

The role of cardinality and neighborhood sampling strategy in agent-based cooperative strategies for Dynamic Optimization Problems

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Abstract

The best performing methods for Dynamic Optimization Problems (DOPs) are usually based on a set of *agents* that can have different complexity (like *solutions* in Evolutionary Algorithms, *particles* in Particle Swarm Optimization, or *metaheuristics* in hybrid cooperative strategies). While methods based on low-complexity agents are widely applied in DOPs, the use of more “intelligent” agents has rarely been explored. This work focuses on this topic and more specifically on the use of cooperative strategies composed by trajectory-based search agents for DOPs. Within this context, we analyze the influence of the number of agents (cardinality) and their neighborhood sampling strategy on the performance of these methods. Using a low number of agents with distinct neighborhood sampling strategies shows the best results. This method is then compared versus state-of-the-art algorithms using as test bed the well-known Moving Peaks Benchmark and dynamic versions of the Ackley’s, Griewank’s and Rastrigin’s functions. The results show that this configuration of the cooperative strategy is competitive with respect to the state-of-the-art methods.

Keywords: Dynamic Optimization Problems, Agent-based optimization, Hybrid Metaheuristics, Cooperative Strategies

1. Introduction

Dynamic Optimization Problems (DOPs) have attracted the attention of the scientific community in the past decade due to its closeness to real-world situations (trade market prediction, meteorological forecast, robotics motion control, etc [1–3]). Solving this type of problems is harder than their “static” counterparts because of the presence of time-dependent properties that may affect the fitness function, constraints, number of variables, their domain, etc.

It is not our purpose here to provide a literature review on the topic (the interested reader is referred to [4] and the website <http://dynamic-optimization.org> for more information) but nowadays, most of the publications in this field consider some assumptions for the resolution of DOPs:

- Changes in the problem can be detected.
- Time-dependent features vary gradually.
- Keeping a good track of the optima is more important than refining the quality of the solutions, especially when the frequency of the changes is high.
- A population of solutions may better track the changes than a unique solution.

Under these assumptions, it is not strange that most of the research is concentrated around population-based methods [2,

5] where each member of the population can be considered as an “agent” in a wide sense. For example, an agent could be a very simple entity as a solution (an individual in the case of Evolutionary Algorithms [6, 7] or a particle in PSO [8, 9]), or a more complex object like a local search operator (mutation operator [10] or a full Tabu Search method [11]).

While methods composed by low-complexity agents are widely extended in DOPs, the use of more sophisticated agents has been less explored. The present work focuses on this last topic and concretely on cooperative strategies where the agents implement trajectory-based algorithms.

Having in mind the need for more competitive methods for solving DOPs, this paper pursues two main objectives. The first one is to analyze two of the features with a higher influence on the performance of cooperative strategies:

- The number of agents composing the strategy, the so called *cardinality*
- The Neighborhood Sampling Strategy (*NSS*) implemented by the agents

To carry out this study, we depart from the approach proposed in [12] where the authors presented a cooperative strategy composed by a set of Tabu Search agents that are controlled by a rule-based central coordinator. In this contribution, the strategy uses the same type of agent.

To evaluate the influence of the cardinality (first feature), we test various configurations with different number of agents. For the second feature, we consider that all the agents can use the same or different *NSS*’s, leading to a homogeneous or a heterogeneous *composition*, respectively. The analysis is done eval-

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uating different pairs {cardinality, composition} over the well-known Moving Peaks Benchmark [1] and dynamic versions of the Ackley’s, Griewank’s and Rastrigin’s continuous optimization functions.

The second objective of the paper is to assess the performance of the best pair {cardinality, composition} by comparing it versus state-of-the-art algorithms for continuous DOPs.

It is important to remark that we will only consider DOPs having changes in the objective function.

This work extends the research presented in [11], [12] and [13], where the same cooperative strategy was used. In the first one, the aim was to study the performance of trajectory-based agents in DOPs as well as the benefits of cooperation; the second work focused on the analysis of different coordination schemas with distinct control rules for this cooperative strategy; and the last paper provided a comparison of several state-of-the-art algorithms for DOPs that included this cooperative strategy, emphasizing the comparison methodology and the visualization of the results.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the cooperative strategy, the Tabu Search implemented by the agents and the NSS’s proposed. The experimental framework is in Section 3, where the benchmark problems, the state-of-the-art methods, the performance measures and the analysis techniques used are presented. Section 4 contains the results related with the first aim of the paper while Section 5 shows the comparison of the best cooperative strategy obtained versus the state-of-the-art algorithms. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 6.

2. A centralized cooperative strategy for Dynamic Optimization Problems

As we stated before, the cooperative strategy used in this paper was previously presented in [11, 12]. In this section, we describe the main aspects of this strategy, the Tabu Search method implemented by the agents and the three Neighborhood Sampling Strategies considered. Further details of the strategy and the Tabu Search method can be found in previous references.

2.1. Description of the cooperative strategy

The strategy consists of a set of agents guided by a central coordinator [12] as shown in Figure 1. The agents explore the search space using a Tabu Search algorithm, periodically sending performance reports to a coordinator which analyses them and readjusts the behavior of the agents by sending orders to them. The orders indicate the agents the point from which they should restart their search, either to move them into more promising region or to escape from a local minimum. The exchange of data is done using a blackboard model [14]. Concretely, two blackboards are available, one to send performance reports from the agents to the coordinator, and another, to send orders from the coordinator to the agents.

Within the cooperative strategy, the coordinator and the agents maintain certain information about the search (e.g. fitness of the current solution, best solution found so far, etc.).

Figure 1: Scheme of the cooperative strategy

Figure 2: Working of the change detection mechanism

When a change is detected by any of the agents, the rest of them should be informed in order to update or discard their search information. The mechanism to detect changes and the system to communicate these changes are described below.

An agent detects fitness function changes by reevaluating its best solution found so far and checking whether its fitness has changed or not. This action is done after each neighborhood exploration to ensure early detection of changes. When an agent i detects a change, it increases a counter cc_i (change counter), that stores the number of changes detected so far (see Figure 2). Then it will send the cc_i value to the coordinator in the next report. The coordinator also maintains a register, called cc_{global} , with the highest cc_i received so far. After receiving a report, the coordinator determines whether the agent has detected a new change ($cc_i > cc_{global}$) to update cc_{global} ; or if it has already perceived the current change ($cc_i = cc_{global}$) or not ($cc_i < cc_{global}$). In the former case, the coordinator notifies those agents that have missed the change to make all the strategy’s components work with current information, as Figure 2 illustrates.

Now, we can describe the cooperative strategy with the help of Figure 3. For the sake of clarity, we divide the description in agents and coordinator:

Agents. At the beginning, the agents are initialized and run asynchronously. Each agent first checks if it has received an order or report from the coordinator. This report contains:

Figure 3: Detailed scheme of the cooperative strategy

- Agent identification
- S_{reloc}
- *changeNotification*

where s_{reloc} can be either a solution from which the agent will restart the search, or an empty value that will be ignored. Regarding *changeNotification*, it is a boolean value set to *True* to inform the agent that a new change was detected.

When the received report has *changeNotification* = *True*, the agent updates its cc_i counter and restarts memories having “obsolete” information as: components of the optimizer (tabu list), the fitness of the current solution, the best solution found so far (S_{best}) and a list where it keeps the local minima found since the last report. These local minima are solutions that could not be improved by the agent after exploring the corresponding neighborhoods a certain number of times. Before running the optimizer, the agent checks if it has to relocate its search ($s_{reloc} \neq \emptyset$) and in this case, it sets its current solution to s_{reloc} .

After a given number of fitness function evaluations, the agent stops the search process, updates the memories, records the performance information in a report and sends it to the coordinator. These performance reports include the following information:

- Agent identification
- S_{best}
- Local minima found since the last report
- cc_i counter

Coordinator. When a report from an agent is available in the input blackboard, the coordinator first checks if the agent has not detected the current change ($cc_i < cc_{global}$). In this case, the agent is notified using an order report. Otherwise, if the agent detected a new change ($cc_i > cc_{global}$), the coordinator resets its memories and updates cc_{global} .

In the next step, the coordinator updates some internal information (memories) using the performance information stored

in the report. Firstly, if s_{best} is better than G_{best} (the global best solution found so far), then $G_{best} \leftarrow s_{best}$.

Secondly, the Visited Region List (VRL) is processed. VRL is a structure where the coordinator keeps the history of the local minima found by all agents. Each entry $v \in \text{VRL}$ is a local minimum that has associated a hypersphere $hyper_v$ centered in v with radius ρ and a counter ϕ_v with the number of times this hypersphere has been visited by any of the agents. ρ is a parameter set by the user and constant along the search process.

The VRL is updated with the list of local minima available in the report. For each local minimum x in the reported list, the coordinator checks if $x \in hyper_v$ for any $v \in \text{VRL}$. If such v exists, then ϕ_v is incremented. In other case, x is added to VRL.

Once the coordinator updates the memories, it applies a set of rules of the form **IF condition THEN relocate agent** to evaluate the performance of the agent as well as the position to be placed to improve its performance (if needed).

In this work we used the best performing rule presented in [11] where the antecedent (condition) was designed using Reactive Search ideas [15] (it was also evaluated in [16] for static domains). Specifically, the control rule implemented by the coordinator is:

<p>IF the last local minimum found by $agent_i$ belongs to a $v \in \text{VRL}$ with $\phi_v > \lambda_{reaction}$</p> <p>THEN relocate $agent_i$ in s_{reloc}</p>

The threshold $\lambda_{reaction}$ regulates the activation of the rule and s_{reloc} is set to the mid-point between G_{best} and s_{best} . The objective of this rule is to move the agent trapped in a local minimum, closer to the best global solution found. If the rule is triggered, the coordinator records the relocation order in a report which is sent to the agent through the output blackboard.

As mentioned before, the optimization method used by the agents is a Tabu Search. The details of this method are described in the next subsection.

2.2. Tabu Search method implemented by the agents

Agents are Tabu Search metaheuristics containing features previously presented in [17] and [18]. From the former we took the variable move step as well as some parts of its tabu neighborhood exploration method and from the latter, its diversification procedure.

An important issue to address in continuous optimization is the step size δ , that is, the maximum distance from the current solution up to which neighborhood solutions are explored. A small step size can lead to an important waste of objective function evaluations, whereas a big step size may avoid finding solutions with enough accuracy. For this reason it is interesting to use a large step size at the beginning of the search to do a better exploration, and then to make it smaller to obtain a better fine tuning of the solution. In this way, the algorithm starts with a step size of length $\delta = \delta_{init}$ and every time the exploration of the neighborhood of the current solution does not lead to a better position, this size is halved. When two consecutive movements lead to improvements in the current solution,

Algorithm 1: Continuous Tabu Search pseudocode

```

1 procedure ContinuousTabuSearch
   $\delta \leftarrow \delta_{init}$ 
   $x \leftarrow \text{GenerateInitialSolution}()$ 
   $x_{best} \leftarrow x$ 
   $x_{cbest} \leftarrow x$ 
   $consAdvances \leftarrow 0$ 

  while not stopping condition do

     $x \leftarrow \text{ExploreNeighborhood}(x, \delta)$ 

    if  $f(x) < f(x_{cbest})$  then
       $x_{cbest} \leftarrow x$ 
       $consAdvances \leftarrow consAdvances + 1$ 
      if  $f(x) < f(x_{best})$  then
         $x_{best} \leftarrow x$ 
      end if
      if  $consAdvances = 2$  then
         $\delta \leftarrow \min(\delta_{init}, \delta \cdot 2)$ 
         $consAdvances \leftarrow 0$ 
      end if
    else
       $\delta \leftarrow \frac{\delta}{2}$ 
    end if
    if  $\delta < res$  then
       $\delta \leftarrow \delta_{init}$ 
      if  $\text{IsNearLocalMinimum}(x_{cbest}, LRR)$  then
         $x \leftarrow \text{Diversification}(x_{cbest})$ 
      else
        { $x_{cbest}$  is considered as a new local minimum}
        AddLocalMinimum( $x_{cbest}$ )
      end if
       $x_{cbest} \leftarrow x$ 
       $consAdvances \leftarrow 0$ 
    end if
  end while

```

the step size is multiplied by two. The length of the movement is delimited by the interval $[res, \delta_{init}]$, where res is a parameter which determines the precision of the algorithm.

Algorithm 1 shows the Tabu Search pseudocode. Let us suppose we are dealing with a minimization problem. After an initialization stage, the Tabu Search iteratively proceeds as follows. Firstly, the loop explores the neighborhood of the current solution and checks whether the chosen neighbor is better than x_{cbest} . If so, the search is allocated at this point and the step size is increased if two consecutive improvements have taken place. Otherwise, δ is halved.

When the step size δ is lower than res , the current solution is identified as a local optimum. Then, the method evaluates whether it is inside a previously visited local minimum (the distance is lower than a parameter named LRR) or not, that is, if it is inside a tabu region or not, respectively. When it is inside a tabu region, the method applies a diversification mechanism (procedure 2.1 of [18]), to restart the search in a non-explored region; otherwise, the Tabu Search stores x_{cbest} as a new local minimum and continues the search from its current point.

Algorithm 2: Neighborhood Exploration pseudocode

```
1 procedure ExploreNeighborhood( $x, \delta$ )  
    $r \leftarrow$  uniform random number in  $[0, 1]$   
   if  $r < P_{add}$  then  
      $x_{new} \leftarrow$  ApproximateDescentDirection( $x, \delta$ )  
   end if  
   if  $r \geq P_{add}$  OR ( $r < P_{add}$  AND  $f(x_{new}) > f(x)$ ) then  
      $x_{new} \leftarrow$  ApplyNeighborhoodSearchStrategy( $x, \delta$ )  
   end if  
   return  $x_{new}$ 
```

The procedure *ExploreNeighborhood* is shown in Algorithm 2. The Tabu Search explores the neighborhood in two different ways that are selected according to a probabilistic criterion. The first one, chosen with probability P_{add} , consists on finding a good descent direction using the Approximate Descent Direction (ADD) method [19] and taking the neighbor at distance δ in that direction. The second one, selected with probability $1 - P_{add}$, consists on the generation of $2n$ solutions by a neighborhood sampling strategy (NSS). A NSS is defined by a neighborhood operator O and a selection operator Γ . The neighborhood operator is an application $O : S \times P \rightarrow S$, where S is the solution space and P is the space of parameters. This operator generates new solutions from a reference solution $X \in S$ in a non deterministic way, that is, various applications of O over the same solution return different solutions. The selection operator $\Gamma : 2^S \times P \rightarrow S$, receives as argument a set of solutions and returns one of them according to certain criteria and parameters. Given a solution X , the NSS works in the following way: it generates $2n$ neighbors applying $2n$ times the operator O over X and then, selects one using Γ . The second exploration mode is also applied every time the ADD mode does not lead to a better solution.

2.3. Neighborhood Sampling Strategies

We chose three NSS's to induce different behaviors to the Tabu Search algorithm. Their descriptions are given below.

2.3.1. Fixed-length Tabu Sampling Strategy (FTSS)

Given a solution $x = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, FTSS generates $2n$ neighbors in the next way: for each coordinate i , two solutions are obtained by adding and by subtracting, only to this coordinate, the current step size δ to x_i (e.g. for $i = 2$, the two solutions generated are $\{x_1, x_2 + \delta, \dots, x_n\}$ and $\{x_1, x_2 - \delta, \dots, x_n\}$). Then, the selection operator returns the best non-tabu solution or the best solution if it fulfills the aspiration level, that is, if it is better than the best solution found so far by the agent. The tabu list is composed by the reverse of the movements previously accepted. A move becomes non-tabu after a given number of iterations defined by the parameter *tenure*, that is set to 1.

2.3.2. Uniform Sampling Strategy (USS)

In this case, the neighborhood operator generates $2n$ solutions uniformly distributed within a hypersphere with radius δ

Table 1: Parameter settings for the continuous Tabu Search. ω is a random value uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$ and x_{range} is the difference between the variables' upper and the lower bounds (assumed equal for all the variables).

Parameter	Description	Value
δ_{init}	initial step size	$x_{range}/3$
res	minimum step size	0.001
LRR	radius for the local minimum regions	$0.01 \cdot x_{range}$
α	step size for diversification procedure	$(0.1 + 0.025 \cdot \omega) \cdot x_{range}$
P_{add}	probability of using ADD neigh. exploration	0.3

and centered at the current solution. The selection operator returns the best generated solution.

2.3.3. Gaussian Sampling Strategy (GSS)

This NSS explores the neighborhood of the current solution by an operator that generates solutions according to a gaussian distribution $N(0, 1)$. Concretely, this operator calculates the i -th component of the new solution by the equation $x_i^{new} = x_i + \delta r$, where x_i is the i -th coordinate of the current solution and r is a gaussian $N(0, 1)$ distributed random number. The selection operator returns the best of the $2n$ neighbors.

2.4. Parameter settings

The Tabu Search parameters are displayed in Table 1 and were selected according to [17, 18]. Regarding the coordinator settings, the radius for the visited regions ρ was set to $\rho = 0.15 \cdot x_{range}$, where x_{range} is the difference between the variables' upper and the lower bounds (assumed equal for all the variables).

The solution s_{reloc} used in the consequent of the control rule is generated as follows: given two solutions $x_1 = \{x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n}\}$ and $x_2 = \{x_{21}, \dots, x_{2n}\}$, each component of the resulting solution z is calculated as $z_i = (x_{1i} + x_{2i})/2, i = 1, \dots, n$.

3. Experimental framework

Different experiments have been performed in order to study the influence of the cardinality and the composition on the performance of the cooperative method. In this section we describe the benchmark functions, the implementation details and the experimental setup.

3.1. Benchmark functions for Dynamic Optimization Problems

3.1.1. The Moving Peaks Benchmark (MPB)

The MPB is a classic test benchmark for DOPs originally proposed in [1]. It is a maximization problem consisting in the superposition of m peaks, each one characterized by its own height (\mathbf{h}), width (\mathbf{w}), and location of its center (\mathbf{p}). The fitness function of the MPB is defined as follows:

$$\text{MPB}(\mathbf{x}) = \max_j \left(h^j - w^j \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - p_i^j)^2} \right), j = 1, \dots, m \quad (1)$$

Table 2: Parameters settings for the MPB, Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin functions.

Parameter	MPB	Ackley	Griewank	Rastrigin
Number of dimensions (n)	{5, 15, 25}			
Change period (ω)	500 · n			
x range	$[0, 100]^n$	$[-32, 32]^n$	$[-50, 50]^n$	$[-5, 5]^n$
Severity (s)	{6%, 12%, 18%} · x range			
Correlation coefficient (λ)	0.5			
Number of peaks (m)	100	-	-	-
Peak heights (h_j)	rand [30, 70]	-	-	-
Peak widths (w_j)	rand [1, 12]	-	-	-
Height severity (h_s)	7.0	-	-	-
Width severity (w_s)	1.0	-	-	-

where n is the dimensionality of the problem. The highest point of each peak corresponds to its center, and therefore, the global optimum is the center of the peak with the highest parameter \mathbf{h} .

Dynamism is introduced in the MPB by periodically changing the parameters of each peak j after a certain number of function evaluations (ω):

$$\mathbf{h}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{h}_j(t) + \mathbf{h}_s \cdot \mathbf{N}(0, 1) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{w}_j(t) + \mathbf{w}_s \cdot \mathbf{N}(0, 1) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_j(t+1) = \mathbf{p}_j(t) + \mathbf{v}_j(t+1) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_j(t+1) = \frac{\mathbf{s}}{|\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{v}_j(t)|} ((1 - \lambda)\mathbf{r} + \lambda \mathbf{v}_j(t)) \quad (5)$$

Changes to both width and height parameters depend on a given severity for each of them (\mathbf{w}_s and \mathbf{h}_s). Changes to the peak position depend on a shift vector $\mathbf{v}_j(t+1)$, which is a linear combination of a random vector \mathbf{r} and the previous shift vector $\mathbf{v}_j(t)$ for the peak, normalized to length \mathbf{s} (position severity, shift distance, or simply *severity*). The random vector \mathbf{r} is created by drawing random numbers for each dimension and normalizing its length to \mathbf{s} . Finally, parameter λ indicates the linear correlation with respect to the previous shift, where a value of 1 indicates “total correlation” and a value of 0 “pure randomness”.

3.1.2. Multimodal continuous functions

One way to obtain artificial dynamic optimization problems is to depart from a “static” function and then add some sort of dynamism. Here, we use standard multimodal functions commonly used in static continuous optimization problems, namely Ackley, Griewank, and Rastrigin, whose expressions are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ackley}(\mathbf{x}) &= -20 \exp \left(-0.2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2} \right) \\ &\quad - \exp \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(2\pi x_i) \right) + 20 + e \quad (6) \\ x_i &\in [-32, 32], \quad x^* = \{0, \dots, 0\} \in \mathbb{R}^n \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Griewank}(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{4000} - \prod_{i=1}^n \cos \left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{i}} \right) + 1 \quad (7) \\ x_i &\in [-50, 50], \quad x^* = \{0, \dots, 0\} \in \mathbb{R}^n \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rastrigin}(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i) + 10) \quad (8) \\ x_i &\in [-5, 5], \quad x^* = \{0, \dots, 0\} \in \mathbb{R}^n \end{aligned}$$

where n is the dimension of the problem, and x^* is the optimum (in all the functions, the optimum is located at the origin of coordinates, the $\{0, \dots, 0\} \in \mathbb{R}^n$).

The dynamism induced to these functions consists in having the origin of coordinates as a parameter, \mathbf{p} , that is changed periodically applying the dynamic model of the MPB described in Equations 4 and 5.

Now, the function to be optimized becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} f'(x) &= f(x - \mathbf{p}) \\ f &\in \{\text{Ackley}, \text{Griewank}, \text{Rastrigin}\} \end{aligned}$$

The main reason to also use these functions in the experimentation is the different nature of their multimodality with respect to the MPB. While the multimodality in the MPB is obtained through the composition of several unimodal functions, Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin are inherently multimodal functions whose composition leads to a very distinct structure, landscape and dynamism of the local optima. For example, whereas in MPB the standard scenarios have up to one hundred local optima (the number of peaks), the other three functions present up to thousands. Besides this, in the MPB problem the local optima are independent from each other. In the dynamic versions of Ackley, Griewank and Rastrigin there are some local optima whose movement is linked (those that belong to the same function) and others that is not (those that belong to different functions). In short, the different landscape and dynamism of these functions provide a wide and heterogeneous benchmark that allows us to accomplish a more robust study.

Figure 4: The boxplot shows the distribution of 50 measures of the e_{off} for 16 different algorithms, ordered by its mean value. Dotted rectangles indicate those algorithms for which no statistical differences were found at a significance level of 0.05. The table on the right displays, for every algorithm, how many times it shows a significantly better performance (“better than”), no significant differences (“equal to”) or significantly worse performance (“worse than”) when it is compared with respect to the other 15 algorithms. Such values are aggregated (“better than” - “worse than”) and its final rank with the correspondent color key is constructed.

3.1.3. Parameter settings for the benchmarks

According to literature, the *dimensionality* and the *severity* of the changes are factors of DOPs that clearly affect the performance of the algorithms. In the experiments conducted in this work, a set of different values for each of the two previous factors were selected and then, every possible combination of values was tested, for every problem, and every algorithm.

The problems’ configurations are summarized in Table 2. These settings are based on the configuration parameters of the so called Scenario 2 of the MPB.

The severity value depends on the range of the input variables x (all x_i dimensions have the same range in the benchmarks), but this range is different for each problem. In order to unify test configurations, the severity values is expressed as a percentage of x ’s range.

3.2. Performance measures

In order to make our results comparable with other closely related works, the performance measure selected for our experiments is the *offline error* (e_{off}) [20]. This measure is the average of the error of the best solution found by the algorithm since the last change, for every function evaluation, and for all changes. Given that the changes in the environment are produced at a fixed rate, its formula is:

$$e_{off} = \frac{1}{N_c N_e} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_e} (f_i^* - f_{ij}) \quad (9)$$

where N_c is the total number of changes in the environment, N_e is the total number of evaluations allowed in each change, f_i^* is the optimum value of the i -th change, and f_{ij} is the best value found by the algorithm since the beginning of the i -th change up to the j -th evaluation.

The execution of an algorithm for N_c changes is defined as a *run*. In order to obtain statistically meaningful results, each experiment consisted of N_r independent runs, each one with a different random seed. In this work, we have chosen $N_r = 50$, and the comparison of the algorithms has been performed using those fifty e_{off} measures for each algorithm.

3.3. Techniques for the analysis of results

3.3.1. A Statistical Ranking Color Scheme (SRCS)

The analysis and visualization of results when comparing algorithms over different DOPs, considering different severities and dimensions, is not a trivial task. Here, we resort to a technique named SRCS, introduced in [21]. SRCS focuses on creating a ranking of the algorithms, instead of displaying the absolute performance values of each one.

The basic idea is as follows. Let us suppose that a set of algorithms are applied over a problem configuration. If a non-parametric test for multiple comparisons detects significant differences among the algorithms, then pairwise comparison tests are performed. For every algorithm, a rank value is calculated using the number of times that such algorithm was better, worse or equal than the others algorithms. After that, a color key is associated to each rank value in order to visually present the results. With the color scheme proposed in SRCS, a lighter color indicates a higher ranking, and therefore, a better performance. This idea is illustrated in Figure 4. These rank colors can then be used instead of numerical values to better compress the information to display when presenting multiple problems / multiple configurations / multiple algorithms results.

We will display the results of our experiments using the SRCS technique and a two level matrix arrangement where the rows and the columns will have a different meaning.

On one hand, we use this two level matrix arrangement to compare the performance of different settings of the coopera-

Figure 5: Rank explanation. A two level matrix arrangement is used to display the results of the SRCS technique. In A) the two level matrix arrangement compares the performance of different settings of the cooperative strategy over a single problem. The rows and columns of the upper level represent possible values for two settings of the cooperative strategy. In the lower level matrices, columns and rows correspond to different configurations for the severity and dimension of the problem, respectively. To check the performance of a given setting over a single problem configuration, we have to compare the colors of the same positions in every lower level matrix, as the black squares show. In B) the two level matrix is used to compare the performance of a set of methods over a set of problems. Upper level rows and columns correspond to methods and problems, respectively. The lower level matrices display the same information as above. To compare the results of various algorithms over a single problem configuration, in this case we have to check the corresponding position of those lower level matrices that belong to the same column as indicated with black squares.

tive strategy over different configurations of a single problem (Figure 5 A). In this case, the rows and columns of the upper level matrix represent possible values for two settings of the cooperative strategy (e.g composition and cardinality). Each lower level matrix shows the results of a specific setup of the cooperative strategy over the different configurations of the problem at hand.

The rows and columns of a lower level matrix represent different configurations for the severity and dimension of the problem, respectively. A cell in this matrix displays the color code returned by the SRCS technique for a set up in a specific problem configuration. To check the performance of a given setting over a single problem configuration, we have to compare the colors of the same positions in every lower level matrix, as Figure 5 A shows with black squares.

In this particular example, we may say that {Feature 1-Value 4, Feature 2- Value 1} obtains the best results (white color) whereas configurations {Feature 1-Value 2, Feature 2-Value 3} and {Feature 1-Value3, Feature 2-Value 4} (darkest color) get the worst rankings.

We will also use a two level matrix for the SRCS results to compare the performance of a set of methods over different configurations of a set of problems (Figure 5 B). In this case, the rows and columns of the upper level matrix are set to methods and problems, respectively. Every low level matrix shows the results obtained by a method in the configurations of a given problem. The lower level matrices display the same information as above. To compare the results of various algorithms over a single problem configuration, in this case we have to check the

corresponding position of those lower level matrices that belong to the same column (as indicated with black squares).

3.3.2. Matched pairs non-parametric tests

The SRCS technique gives statistical information about the ranking of a set of methods in just one configuration of one problem. However, it is also interesting to compare the results of the methods over a *set* of configurations from one or various problems to have a more comprehensive view. In this sense, García et al. proposed in [22] the directives to carry out this global analysis using paired non-parametric statistical tests. These tests allow to rank the performance of two or more methods over a set of problem configurations and to determine if the differences in performance are significant or not. The significance of the differences is assessed by comparing estimators (usually the mean/median fitness or error value) of the performance of the algorithms over each problem configuration.

Matched pairs non-parametric tests allow, for example, to determine the best global method over all the configurations of the MPB problem or over the 36 problem configuration considered in this work. The specific matched pairs non-parametric tests used here were provided by the tool KEEL [23]. We used *Friedman's test* to determine if there are significant differences between the performance of two or more methods, *Holm's test* to detect which algorithms are worse than a control algorithm, and *Wilcoxon paired test* to check if there exist significance differences between the performance of two algorithms.

4. Results

The first objective of the contribution is to study the influence that the number of agents (cardinality) and the composition (in terms of the NSS's) have on the performance of the cooperative strategy described in Section 2.

Four values of cardinality were considered: 3, 6, 9 and 12. For each of them, we studied four variants of composition. Three of them correspond to a homogeneous assignment of the three NSS's seen in Section 2.3. The fourth is a heterogeneous composition where the three NSS are equally distributed among the agents (e.g.: for a cardinality of 6, the composition is $2 \times FTSS + 2 \times USS + 2 \times GSS$). Thereby we have 16 cardinality-composition pairs. Apart from this, both the independent (there is no cooperation among the agents) and the cooperative version of these instances of the strategy will be analyzed, so we evaluate 32 different methods. The next notation will be used to refer to these methods:

$\{\textit{cooperation}\}-\{\textit{cardinality}\}-\{\textit{composition}\}-\{\textit{NSS}\}$

The description of the items and their possible values are the following:

- Cooperation indicates if the method is cooperative (C) or independent (I)
- Cardinality is a numerical value in the set $\{3,6,9,12\}$
- Composition indicates if the strategy is homogeneous (HM) or Heterogeneous (HT)
- If Composition = HM, then NSS indicates which NSS is implemented by the agents.

If an item is omitted, then we will refer to a set of methods that includes all the possible values of such item. For example, C-3 refers to the set of the cooperative strategies with three agents: $\{C-3-HT, C-3-HM-FTSS, C-3-HM-USS, C-3-HM-GSS\}$; and I-HM-GSS refers to the set of the independent methods with homogeneous GSS composition: $\{I-3-HM-GSS, I-6-HM-GSS, I-9-HM-GSS, I-12-HM-GSS\}$.

The methods were tested over the 36 configurations (4 problems \times 3 severity levels \times 3 dimensions) stated in Section 3.1.3. The analysis is structured in three parts: first, we study the influence of the cardinality and the composition on the performance of the strategy; then, we analyze the effect of these two elements in the cooperation; and finally we determine the best cardinality-composition pair.

4.1. Influence of the cardinality and the composition on the performance

To carry out this analysis, we compared the 16 cardinality-composition pairs using the independent version of the strategy on the one hand and the cooperative version on the other hand. In this way, we study the influence of the cardinality and the composition with and without a cooperation bias. The results are first analyzed using the SRCS technique and then, by means of the matched pairs non-parametric tests seen in Section 3.3.2.

Figure 6 shows the SRCS plots for the MPB benchmark. Each row corresponds to a composition whereas each column

indicates the cardinality. Starting with the independent strategies displayed in Figure 6 A and focusing on the compositions, we observe that I-HM-GSS obtains the best results for high dimensions (15 and 25) and achieves at least as good performance as their counterparts for dimension 5. I-HT (the heterogeneous version) is the second best alternative, only improved by I-HM-GSS. This indicates that the NSS's do not have a complementary behavior in I-HT: the performance is mainly due to those agents that use GSS as their neighborhood sampling strategy. The other two compositions have a similar performance excepting cardinality three where I-HM-USS is more effective than I-HM-FTSS.

Focusing now on the cardinality, a very interesting result can be observed: the lower the cardinality, the better the performance. Regardless of the composition, increasing the number of agents leads to a performance degradation in virtually all the configuration of the MPB benchmark. This trend is also detected in the other test problems (Figures 7, 8 and 9).

Figure 6 B shows the results when cooperation is used in the MPB benchmark. In general, the performance of the methods in terms of composition and cardinality is similar to those presented for the independent scheme.

In the dynamic version of Ackley's function the results are quite different (Figure 7). In this case, HM-FTSS is the best composition for all cardinalities and for both the independent and the cooperative methods. The HT composition also shows good results especially when cooperation is activated. I-HM-USS is better than I-HM-GSS although their performance is virtually the same when cooperation is used.

Figure 8 shows that in the Griewank problem the dominant composition varies from one problem configuration to another. For dimensions 15 and 25, HM-GSS is the best performing composition, especially when the number of agents is three, whereas for the lowest dimension, I-HM-USS and C-HM-FTSS show the best results in the independent and cooperative cases, respectively.

The scenario we find in the Rastrigin's function is similar to the one we saw in Ackley's problem (see Figure 9): HM-FTSS is the best composition, followed by HT, HM-USS and HM-GSS in that order.

4.2. Study of the influence of cardinality and composition on the cooperation

In the preceding subsection, independent and cooperative methods have been studied separately. In this section, we compare cooperative versus independent variants of the strategy to assess the role of cooperation and to analyze whether the benefits of cooperation (if any) depend on the cardinality and the composition.

We performed a pair-wise comparison between the independent and the cooperative version of the 16 configurations $\{\textit{composition}, \textit{cardinality}\}$ pairs, first on each problem and then globally over the four problems. In both cases, the comparison is done by means of the Wilcoxon's matched-pairs signed-ranks test at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ following the directives given in [22].

Figure 7: Rank results of all the {cardinality-composition} pairs for ACKLEY's function using the independent (A) and the cooperative (B) versions of the strategy. See Section 3.2 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

Table 3: Pair-wise comparison between the independent and the cooperative version of the 16 cardinality-composition pairs by means of the Wilcoxon’s matched-pairs signed-ranks, taking as samples the mean e_{off} obtained in the different configurations, for MPB, Ackley, Griewank, Rastrigin and globally over the four problems. Symbol – stands for no statistical differences, > indicates that the cooperative version significantly improves the independent one and < means the opposite (confidence level of 0.95)

	Composition	Cardinality			
		3	6	9	12
MPB	HT	–	–	–	–
	HM-FTSS	–	–	–	–
	HM-GSS	>	>	–	–
	HM-USS	–	–	–	–
Ackley	HT	>	>	>	>
	HM-FTSS	>	–	–	>
	HM-GSS	>	>	>	>
	HM-USS	>	>	>	>
Griewank	HT	>	>	–	–
	HM-FTSS	>	–	–	–
	HM-GSS	–	>	>	–
	HM-USS	–	–	–	–
Rastrigin	HT	<	–	–	–
	HM-FTSS	<	–	–	–
	HM-GSS	>	>	>	>
	HM-USS	>	>	>	>
Global	HT	–	–	>	>
	HM-FTSS	–	–	–	–
	HM-GSS	>	>	>	>
	HM-USS	>	>	>	>

For the first analysis, we considered nine samples per algorithm and problem, which correspond to the mean e_{off} values (over 50 runs) obtained by the algorithm in the nine configurations of the problem. Table 3 displays the results of this comparison, where – stands for no statistical differences, > indicates that the cooperative version significantly improves the independent one and < means the opposite. The first point to highlight is the strong variation of the results from one problem to another. In the MPB, cooperation only produces significant benefits on 2 out of 16 methods. On the contrary, the role of cooperation is clear in Ackley’s function. In this case, the cooperative variant of all methods (excepting 6-HM-FTSS and 9-HM-FTSS), provides significant improvements with respect to the independent counterpart. In the Griewank problem, the cooperative version significantly reduces the e_{off} in lower cardinalities for HT and HM-FTSS and in intermediate cardinalities for GSS. Finally, in Rastrigin’s function, the influence of the cooperation is independent of the cardinality for HM-GSS and HM-USS since the improvement is significant in all cases. The other two compositions present a different scenario. The non-cooperative methods obtain significantly better results for cardinality three. In summary, we can clearly observe that cooperation is useful, or at least not harmful, in 62 out of 64 cases.

In order to obtain a global vision of the performance of the cooperation as a function of cardinality and composition, we take as samples, for the Wilcoxon’s matched pairs non-

Table 4: Comparison among cooperative methods with 3 agents. The method displayed in the row is considered as the control algorithm for the Holm’s post-hoc test in each case. > indicates that the method in the row significantly improves the method of the column, < means the opposite and “-” is displayed when the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The significance level is $\alpha = 0.05$

Composition (C-3-)	Mean Ranking	HT	HM-FTSS	HM-GSS	HM-USS
HT	2.08		-	-	>
HM-FTSS	2.25	-		-	>
HM-GSS	2.67	<	-		-
HM-USS	3.00	<	-	-	

parametric test, the mean e_{off} value for the 36 problem configurations (4 problems \times 9 configurations). Table 3 shows these results in the last four rows. The cardinality only affects the heterogeneous composition, showing that the cooperative version is useful when high cardinality values (9 and 12) are used. On the contrary, cardinality has no effects on the other three compositions: cooperation always produces significant improvements for HM-GSS and HM-USS, and never for HM-FTSS.

4.3. Analysis of the best cardinality-composition pair

This analysis aims to establish which is the best global {cardinality-composition} pair from the 32 alternatives studied above. For the sake of simplicity, this study focuses on cooperative methods with cardinality 3 since globally, they obtained similar or significantly better results than their independent and higher cardinality counterparts.

For this study we have used Friedman’s test for multiple comparisons and Holm’s post-hoc test for the pairwise comparisons, following again the guidelines given in [22], and both at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The Friedman’s test rejected the null hypothesis of no differences among the performance of the methods. Table 4 displays the mean ranking for each method and the pairwise comparisons using the Holm’s post-hoc test. In this table, the method displayed in the row is considered as the control algorithm, for the Holm’s post-hoc test, in each case. Again, > indicates that the method in the row significantly improves the method in the column, < means the opposite and “-” is displayed when the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The mean ranking values show that the best global composition is C-3-HT despite of not being the best particular method in any of the four problems considered. This proves that its behavior is fairly robust to changes in the landscape or dynamism of the problem configurations. C-3-HT shows a difference in performance that is significant with respect to C-3-HM-USS. Regarding the homogeneous methods, C-3-HM-FTSS is the best one, followed by C-3-HM-GSS and C-3-HM-USS. In this case, the null hypothesis of similar performance can only be rejected when C-3-HM-FTSS and C-3-HM-USS are compared. Summarizing, C-3-HT is the recommended alternative (although it cannot be probed statistically) so this is the method that will be compared versus state-of-the-art algorithms for DOPs.

Figure 10: Rank results of C-3-HT and the state-of-the-art algorithms for the MPB, Ackley's, Griewank's and Rastrigin's functions. See section 3.2 for a detailed explanation of the ranking method.

Table 5: Comparison of C-3-HT versus high performance algorithms using Holm’s post hoc procedure

Algorithm	z	p-value	α/i	Sig.Diff?
mqso	7.692181	10^{-14}	0.0083	Yes
mqso-change	6.928418	10^{-14}	0.0100	Yes
soriga	6.655646	10^{-14}	0.0125	Yes
mqso-rand	6.164655	10^{-14}	0.01667	Yes
mqso-both	5.946438	10^{-14}	0.02500	Yes
agents	4.037031	5.4×10^{-5}	0.0500	Yes

5. Comparison versus the state-of-the-art algorithms

The second objective of this paper is to compare the best {cardinality-composition} pair, that is, C-3-HT, to check if it can compete with some high-performing algorithms for DOPs. These methods are:

- SORIGA [6]: a genetic algorithm using two different populations.
- Agents [10, 24]: a decentralized cooperative strategy where each agent operates as a mutation operator.
- mQSO [3]: a multi quantum particle swarm optimization, that employs two types of particles (trajectory and quantum)
- mQSO + Change Rule [25]: an extension of mQSO that dynamically adjusts the proportions of trajectory and quantum particles.
- mQSO + Rand Rule [25]: an extension of mQSO that can move or stop swarms showing a bad performance.
- mQSO + Both Rules: a mQSO using the previous two extensions.

A detailed description of the methods is provided as supplementary material at the end of the contribution.

For the computational experiments, we considered the same problems and configurations used in the former analysis.

First, we use the SRCS plots to obtain a detailed vision of the comparison. These graphics, displayed in Figure 10, clearly indicate that C-3-HT outperforms the other algorithms in all the configurations of Ackley’s, Griewank’s and Rastrigin’s functions.

In the MPB benchmark, C-3-HT’s performance is statistically the best in 5 out of 9 configurations. The method mqso-rand achieved the best results for dimension 5 and severity 6%, and the Agents algorithms for dimension 15 and severity 18%.

To finish with this comparison, we will check if C-3-HT is the best overall method using Holm’s post hoc statistical analysis taking this strategy as control algorithm. Table 5 displays all the computations associated with this test (z , p-value and α/i) at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The last column indicates whether the difference in performance with the control algorithm is significant or not. In view of these results, we can conclude that C-3-HT offers very competitive results since Holm’s

test establishes that it significantly improves the seven high performance algorithms when the results over all configurations are considered.

6. Conclusions

This work focused on cooperative methods for DOPs that are based on a set of cooperating agents that implement trajectory-based optimization methods (Tabu Search here).

In first place, the contribution presented an analysis of the influence of the number of agents (cardinality) and composition (in terms of the neighborhood sampling strategy) on the global performance of the strategy. After an extensive experimentation over four problems and considering nine different combinations of severity and dimensionality, the main conclusions obtained are the next ones:

- The lower the cardinality, the better the performance: strategies with just three agents outperformed those with a higher number of agents.
- The “best” NSS depends to a larger extent on the problem than on the dimension or severity of the configuration.
- The heterogeneous compositions showed a more robust behavior, over the four problems, than the homogeneous ones despite not being the best performing option in none of them.
- The global best performing {cardinality-composition} pair was the heterogeneous composition with 3 agents.

This heterogeneous strategy with 3 agents was compared against some of the best performing methods for DOPs. This comparison revealed the cooperative strategy significantly outperforms the seven algorithms considered.

The main trend in DOPs is the development of methods that consist of a relatively large number of agents. The wide number of population based Evolutionary Algorithms or Particle Swarm Optimization methods for DOPs found in the literature supports the former claim. However, as it was already pointed out in [11], if the number of agents is reduced but their “intelligence” is increased, very competitive results can also be obtained. The study presented in this work can be considered as a step forward in this direction, since we have shown that only three agents properly coordinated improve significantly some of the best performing algorithms for DOPS.

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Supplementary Material:Description of algorithms

The descriptions of those high performance algorithms used in this work are given below. These methods have been implemented in Java following the guidelines given by their authors. Their source codes as well as the source code of the cooperative strategy are available upon request.

Multi Quantum Particle Swarm Optimization (mQSO, standard approach)

The mQSO [3] is a variant of the classical particle swarm optimization (PSO) [27] algorithm, developed by Blackwell and Branke to specifically cope with DOP’s. The general idea of the mQSO is to use a set of multiple swarms that simultaneously explore the search space. Every swarm in the mQSO is formed by two types of particles: trajectory (t) and quantum (q) particles. The former, also known as classical particles, move according to the standard rules of PSO. The latter are aimed at providing a higher level of diversity, moving randomly around the best solution in the swarm.

The parameter settings used in the standard mQSO are summarized in Table 6. Please note that the next three variants of the mQSO share most of these settings, with the exception of the t-q particles ratio, a fact that is also reflected in Table 6. These settings are based on the standard ones used in the literature, defined in [3] and [26].

The mQSO + Change Rule

The original mQSO is extended here with a rule that adjusts the proportions of each particle type during the run according to an approximation of their expected performance. This proposal was presented in [25].

The settings for the algorithm are summarized in Table 7, and extend the ones shown in Table 6, also applied to this method.

The mQSO + Rand Rule

This extension of mQSO was also proposed in [25]. The *Rand Rule* is oriented to stop or relocate those swarms showing a “bad performance”. The motivation behind this rule is

Table 6: Parameter settings for all mQSO variants

Parameter	mqso	mqso-change	mqso-rand	mqso-both
Number of swarms	5			
Number of particles/swarm	10			
Number of q-particles	2	variable	2	variable
Number of t-particles	8	variable	8	variable
c_1, c_2	2.05 (as recommended in [26])			
χ	0.729843788 (as recommended in [26])			
q-particles radius	12% of x_{range}			
Inter-swarm exclusion distance	1.2% of x range			

Table 7: Parameter settings for mQSO + Change Rule

Parameter	Value
θ_d	15% of total duration of θ
θ_d min. duration	5 iterations
θ_c	85% of total duration of θ
α	0.6
β	0.8

to avoid the wasting of function evaluations in non-promising regions of the search space.

The parameter settings are summarized in Table 8, and extend the ones shown in Table 6, which are also applied to this method.

Table 8: Parameter settings for mQSO + Rand Rule

Parameter	Value
Min. improvement ratio	15% of historical maximum
Max. low improvement count	5
Percentage for <i>bad</i> performance	20%
Min. available time	20% of total duration of θ

The mQSO + Both Rules

This algorithm combines the two previous extensions proposed for mQSO and uses their same settings.

Self Organized Random Immigrants Genetic Algorithm

This method, known as SORIGA, was proposed by Tinós and Yang in [6]. It is a population based method that uses two different populations: the main population and a sub-population. Individuals are dynamically assigned to populations during runtime, and crossover is only allowed between individuals within the same population.

Here we adapted the original SORIGA method (tested on combinatorial problems) to deal with continuous DOPs, simply meaning that reasonable good crossover and mutation operators should be used instead of the original ones. As crossover operator we use BLX- α . As mutation operator, a random mutation is used: the value of just one variable in the individual is replaced

by a random number uniformly distributed in the corresponding variable range.

The parameter settings for this algorithm are displayed in Table 9. They are basically the same as those proposed in the original paper, with the exception of the population size. Some preliminary tests showed that a smaller value than the original one provided better results.

Table 9: Parameter settings for the SORIGA algorithm

Parameter	Value
Population size	50
Elite size	2
Replacement rate (r_r)	0.02
Mutation rate (r_m)	0.01
Crossover rate (r_c)	0.7
α (for the BLX- α operator)	1.0

The Agents algorithm

The Agents algorithm is a decentralized cooperative strategy that was originally described in [10, 24]. The algorithm consists of a set of agents (that can be understood as mutation operators) that move in a fixed-size matrix, or *grid*, of solutions. When an agent arrives to a cell in the matrix, it takes the corresponding solution and tries to improve it. If an improvement is achieved, the modified solution is returned back to the matrix. Agents movement and information management depend on the neighbors of the cell that are determined by the topology of the *neighborhood* (in this case, a Moore neighborhood). The parameter settings used in the experimentation for the Agents algorithm are summarized in Table 10, and were determined according to the settings used in [10, 24].

Table 10: Parameter settings for the Agents algorithm

Parameter	Value
Number of rows	5
Number of columns	10
Number of agents	4
Perturbation radius	14% of x_{range}